

Nutritional Guidelines for Women During Lactation

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Abstract

Lactation is a physiological state in which a woman's requirements for energy, nutrients, and water change [1]. A balanced diet during this period will help maintain health, prevent the development of deficiencies, and support the reduction of adipose tissue accumulated during pregnancy. There are many myths about nutrition during lactation passed down from generation to generation. The vast majority of them have no scientific or practical justification and represent unnecessary restrictions [2].

Introduction

Breastfeeding is recognized by the World Health Organization (WHO), the American Academy of Pediatrics (AAP), and the European Society for Paediatric Gastroenterology, Hepatology and Nutrition (ESPGHAN) as the optimal nutrition for infants at least until 6 months of age, and its continuation in subsequent months of the child's life is recommended, taking into account the stages of complementary feeding [3, 4, 4a, 5]. In 2025, during the 78th World Health Assembly, WHO raised the global exclusive breastfeeding target from 50% (target for 2025) to 60% by 2030, emphasizing the importance of breastfeeding as the most effective preventive intervention for child health and survival [3a].

Changes in nutrient requirements for breastfeeding mothers must be considered throughout the lactation period. A low-energy diet, unbalanced in terms of nutritional value, can lead to nutritional deficiencies including magnesium, calcium, zinc, fat-soluble vitamins (A, D, K) and water-soluble vitamins (C, B1, B6, B12, B9) [6].

1. Energy Value of the Diet

To produce milk with an energy value of approximately 70 kcal/100 ml, a woman needs additional energy. The daily energy expenditure of a breastfeeding woman is determined to be approximately 2.8 MJ (670 kcal) per day during the first six months postpartum [1]. Approximately 2.1 MJ (500 kcal) of additional energy should be provided from food, and the remaining amount of approximately 670 kJ (165 kcal) in well-nourished mothers should come from their adipose tissue reserves. Lean mothers may need to increase the energy value of their diet by up to 650 kcal/day compared to their pre-pregnancy energy requirements [1]. If a woman continues breastfeeding as a supplement to infant feeding, she also needs additional energy. This depends on the amount of milk produced, but it is estimated to be approximately 400 kcal [1, 7].

2. Macronutrient Content

a) Protein

Protein requirements during lactation increase compared to the pre-pregnancy period [1]. It should constitute approximately 20% of daily requirements [7, 7a]. A predominance of animal-source protein in the diet is recommended: lean meat, fish, eggs, dairy products. Legume seeds, which are a source of plant protein, are also a desirable element of the diet [9]. The diet of a breastfeeding mother has all the characteristics of a healthy diet, therefore consumption of more than 500 g of red meat per week is not recommended [1].

b) Fats

Fat content in the diet should be approximately 30-40% of daily requirements (20-30% for individuals with low physical activity), during lactation it increases by an amount dependent on baseline fat intake in the diet [1]. The diet should be dominated by sources of polyunsaturated fatty acids: high-quality vegetable oils (preferably cold-pressed), consumed raw, unprocessed nuts, and fatty marine fish such as herring, mackerel, and sprat. Fish with potentially higher heavy metal content, which include long-lived species such as tuna, shark, and swordfish, should be consumed less frequently [1]. Rapeseed oil and olive oil are suitable for heating at high temperatures. Sources of saturated fatty acids such as lard, bacon, fatty meats, and tropical oils (coconut, palm) should be limited, and trans fats (partially hydrogenated vegetable oils) should be completely eliminated, as they pass into breast milk and can negatively affect the infant [7, 23]. Docosahexaenoic acid (DHA) influences the development of the brain, nervous system, retina, and immune system in infants [10], therefore daily supplementation of 200-300 mg/d is recommended, and in case of low consumption of fish, which are its main source - 400-600 mg/d [7, 11].

c) Carbohydrates

Carbohydrate requirements should be approximately 45-65% of daily requirements [1]. Complex carbohydrates should predominate, sources of which are whole grain products: groats, whole grain bread, whole grain pasta, unprocessed cereal flakes. Sources of simple carbohydrates should be limited: sweets, sweetened beverages, sugar.

3. Micronutrient Requirements

Requirements for certain vitamins and minerals increase compared to the pre-pregnancy period (Table 1). Others remain unchanged [1].

Table 1. Vitamin and mineral requirements during lactation [1, 12]

Nutrient	Requirements according to 2024 Standards	Dietary Source [12]	Supplementation – rationale, values
Calcium	<19 years: 1300 mg ≥19 years: 1000 mg	Dairy, mineral water, kale, sardines, calcium-fortified plant-based beverages	In case of insufficient dietary intake, e.g., cow's milk protein allergy. The most bioavailable supplement forms are amino acid chelates such as citrate, carbonate, acetate
Vitamin D3	n/a	Fish, eggs, cod liver oil	Supplementation for breastfeeding women with vitamin D3 deficiency in diet or limited skin synthesis in amounts of 800-1000 IU (1200-2000 IU) [13]
Iodine	290 mcg	Iodized salt, fish, algae	No need for supplementation, as sufficient amounts will be consumed from fortified food
Iron	20 mg/d [7]	Meat, fish, eggs, legume seeds, nuts, green plants	Justified only in case of a diet poor in the nutrient, after determining that it is not possible

			to provide it in natural form, e.g., vegetarian diet
Vitamin A	<19 years: 1200 mcg ≥19 years: 1300 mcg	Green vegetables, carrots, peppers, peaches, apricots	
Vitamin E	11 mg	Rapeseed oil, walnuts	
Vitamin C	<19 years: 115 mg ≥19 years: 120 mg	Vegetables and fruits	
Vitamin B1	1.5 mg	Beans, beef, liver	
Vitamin B2	1.6 mg	Dairy, eggs, mushrooms	
Niacin	17 mg	Meat, fish, green plants, nuts	
Vitamin B6	2 mg	Whole grain cereals, nuts, legume seeds	
Folate	500 mcg	Vegetables and fruits	

Vitamin B12	2.8 mcg	Meat, fish, eggs	Justified only in case of a diet poor in the nutrient, after determining that it is not possible to provide it in natural form, e.g., vegetarian diet
Biotin	35 mcg	Meat, bananas, tomatoes, nuts	
Pantothenic acid	7 mg	Eggs, offal, cruciferous vegetables	
Phosphorus	<19 years: 1250 mg ≥19 years: 700 mg	Cereal products, dairy, fish, eggs, meat	
Magnesium	<19 years: 360 mg ≥19 years: 320 mg	Whole grain cereals, beets, cocoa, mineral water	
Zinc	<19 years: 13 mg ≥19 years: 12 mg	Meat, seeds, nuts, seafood	
Copper	1.3 mg	Green vegetables, nuts, seeds, seafood	

Selenium	70 mcg	Whole grain products, nuts (especially Brazil nuts)	
Manganese	2.6 mg	Nuts, whole grain products	
Potassium	4000 mg	Banana, tomatoes, avocado	
Molybdenum	65 µg [1]	Legumes, whole grain products, offal, asparagus	

4. Water

In women whose children are exclusively breastfed, average milk production ranges between 500 and 900 ml/day during the first six months postpartum [1]. Water and other fluid requirements average approximately 2700-3000 ml/d [1, 14, 15]. The most favorable choice is medium-mineralized water with an optimal ratio between sodium and other minerals [15].

5. Vegetarian Diet During Lactation

Due to the increasingly common vegetarian diet among pregnant and breastfeeding women, the need to monitor nutritional status and adequate intake of vitamin B12, vitamin D, calcium, iron, DHA fatty acids, and protein is emphasized, especially as dietary restrictions become more stringent [16, 17, 18].

6. Preventing Infant Discomfort Through Maternal Elimination Diet

The use of elimination diets during pregnancy and lactation is not justified according to current scientific consensus [19]. Review studies do not find associations between elimination diets (lactose-free, dairy-free) and prevention of atopy and allergies in children, even when parents are allergic [20], therefore restricting certain food groups for the purpose of allergy prevention in children is unjustified. An indication for implementing an elimination diet would only be confirmed food allergy in the infant [21, 22].

Interrupting breastfeeding during infant colic is unfavorable in light of current knowledge [7]. Breast milk reduces infant colic symptoms and prolongs nighttime sleep through increased melatonin content in nighttime breast milk [23]. Allergens, caffeine, alcohol, active drug substances, and some preservatives will pass into milk [24]. Complete elimination of alcohol from the breastfeeding woman's diet is recommended, while caffeine consumption should be limited to 300 mg, which corresponds to 3 cups of coffee or 6 cups of tea [7, 24]. Oligosaccharides that undergo fermentation in the large intestine are molecules too large to pass into milk. There are clear recommendations toward diversifying the diet with potentially gas-producing products: legume seeds and cruciferous vegetables [1, 7]. The current expert consensus [7, 7a] indicates no association between colic occurrence and the presence of legume seeds and cruciferous vegetables in the mother's diet, although there are researchers who continue to investigate this topic, indicating the need for further studies to examine whether a low-FODMAP diet contributes to alleviating infant colic symptoms [25]. However, it is worth limiting processed food both due to its low nutritional value and the risk of excessive food additives [21, 24].

7. Factors Affecting Lactation

Among factors negatively affecting lactation, nicotine is mentioned. Smoking itself is not a contraindication to breastfeeding, but it significantly affects the volume of milk produced [7, 24]. Cigarette smoking can reduce the volume of milk produced by up to 200-300 ml. Therefore, complete cessation of smoking or significant reduction in the number of cigarettes smoked daily is suggested.

To stimulate lactation, women often resort to substances called galactagogues, however, their action, effects, and safety have not been fully elucidated and confirmed [7, 26]. The most commonly used in Poland, i.e., fenugreek, fennel, wild asparagus, show negative health effects, which calls for very cautious use of such preparations [27]. Among substances with a better documented safety profile is β -glucan – a polysaccharide found in oats, barley, and brewer's yeast (*Saccharomyces cerevisiae*). Preliminary clinical studies suggest that its action may be related to modulation of the immune response, which is often disturbed in mothers after preterm birth [29]. In a randomized controlled trial involving mothers of premature infants, the use of a barley malt-based preparation containing β -glucan was associated with significantly higher milk production compared to placebo (difference ~1800 ml/14 days), although the study was characterized by significant loss of participants to follow-up [28]. The ongoing multicentre BLOOM study aims to verify these observations and assess the safety of long-term β -glucan use in this patient group [29]. So far, a substance whose negative health effects have not been described are polysaccharides found in barley malt, hence it is mentioned as a useful dietary component for women experiencing lactation problems [7, 2].

8. Summary

Lactation is a process requiring increased amounts of energy, nutrients, and water in a woman's diet. Focus should be placed on balancing the diet in terms of energy (which will support reduction of adipose tissue accumulated during pregnancy), macronutrients, and micronutrients, taking into account changes in requirements. When composing a menu, focus should be on variety rather than unjustified restrictions. Greater attention to nutritional

education and cooperation with a dietitian for women during pregnancy and lactation is justified to increase their awareness and minimize the chances of implementing false recommendations from various sources. Such action will increase their quality of life, reduce stress, and reduce the chances of developing nutritional deficiencies.

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